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0.025M solution was prepared by dissolving DIH in anhydrous glacial acetic acid (9.5g dm⁻³) and kept in an amber coloured bottle. The solution was standardised daily by the usual iodometric method². Standard solutions of the reductants were prepared in appropriate solvents as described earlier^{6,9} and were checked by standard methods^{10,11}.

For potentiometric titrations the apparatus and electrode assemblies were as described earlier⁶. The usual procedures for the potentiometric, direct visual and excess back titrations were used.

Results and Discussion

Typical results of the titrations are presented in Table 1. The reduction half reaction of DIH is represented by the equation

where R=C₆H₆O₂. The product was found to be the hydantoin. The conditional redox potential of DIH in glacial acetic acid at 29° was +1.07 V.

Diiodohydantoin as a New Oxidimetric Titrant for Use in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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IN continuation of our work for the development of new redox titrants¹⁻⁶, we are now introducing diiodohydantoin, 1,3-diiodo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin (DIH), for the use as an oxidimetric titrant in aqueous acetic acid medium. Direct potentiometric titrations are developed using DIH as the titrant for the determination of arsenic(III), antimony(III), tin(II), ferrocyanide, thiocyanate, sulphite, ascorbic acid, hydrazine, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, hydroquinone, Reinecke's salt, mercury(II)-tetrathio-cyanato cobaltate(II) and mercury(II)-tetrathio-cyanato zincate(II). Direct visual titrations are developed for ascorbic acid, hydrazine, semicarbazide and Reinecke's salt. Direct titrations are unsuccessful for mercury(I), isonicotinic acid hydrazide, thiosemicarbazide, thiourea, phenol and aniline, for which excess back titrations are developed using DIH as the titrant.

Experimental

DIH was prepared by the iodination of 5,5-dimethylhydantoin as per the reported method⁷. It is sparingly soluble in water, but is fairly so in glacial acetic acid (19.8 g/kg at 29°). Approximately

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATIONS WITH DIODOHYDANTOIN

Reductant	Titrimetric method	Range of reductant taken m mol	Standard deviation* μ mol	Maximum error %
As ³⁺	b	0.05-0.17	0.30	0.47
Sb ³⁺	b	0.13-0.41	0.16	0.30
Sn ²⁺	b	0.11-0.21	0.20	0.36
Ferrocyanide	b	0.20-0.61	0.66	0.45
Thiocyanate	b	0.25-0.77	0.12	0.40
Sulphite	b	0.55-1.10	0.10	0.44
Ascorbic acid	a	0.39-0.86	2.40	0.40
	b	0.16-0.31	0.20	0.39
Hydrazine	a	0.24-0.74	2.90	0.36
	b	0.09-0.20	0.05	0.48
Phenylhydrazine	b	0.07-0.12	0.30	0.45
Semicarbazide	a	0.14-0.28	2.70	0.40
	b	0.05-0.09	0.18	0.40
Hydroquinone	b	0.16-0.27	0.20	0.40
Reinecke's salt	a	0.03-0.08	3.10	0.40
	b	0.01-0.02	0.02	0.40
Hg[Co(SCN) ₄]	b	0.004-0.015	0.04	0.41
Hg[Zn(SCN) ₄]	b	0.005-0.010	0.02	0.50
Hg ²⁺	c	0.50-1.01	3.20	0.40
Isonicotinic acid-hydrazide	c	0.10-0.23	2.80	0.44
Thiosemicarbazide	c	0.03-0.13	1.70	0.17
Thiourea	c	0.03-0.13	0.40	0.09
Phenol	c	0.01-0.20	1.70	0.40
Aniline	c	0.01-0.14	2.30	0.40

a Direct starch indicator, b Direct potentiometric, c Back titration, * Ten replicates.

The results show that all the titrations are very accurate and precise. In the potentiometric titrations of all but tin(II), sulphite and ascorbic acid, addition of 5 ml of saturated mercuric chloride solution is essential for the success of the titrations. So is the case with the direct visual titrations of the four reductants studied. The function of mercuric chloride in these cases is probably to remove the

iodide formed during the reactions and hence to shift the reactions forward¹³.

The reductants, mercury(I), isonicotinic acid hydrazide, thiosemicarbazide, thiourea, phenol and aniline could only be determined by excess back titrations. A period of 5 min is needed for the completion of the oxidation in these cases.

All the reductants studied undergo the usual oxidation schemes reported earlier^{8,9,11}. As expected from their usual oxidation schemes, 1 equivalent of oxidant is consumed per mole of ferrocyanide and mercury(I); 2 equivalents for arsenic(III), antimony(III), tin(II), sulphite, ascorbic acid and hydroquinone; 4 equivalents for hydrazine, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide and isonicotinic acid hydrazide (only the hydrazine parts are oxidised); 6 equivalents for thiocyanate, phenol and aniline; 8 equivalents for thiourea; 10 equivalents for thiosemicarbazide; and 24 equivalents for Reinecke's salt and mercury(II) tetrathiocyanates of cobaltate(II) and zincate(II). These three complex thiocyanates have four thiocyanate groups each.

As per the proposed oxidation schemes, arsenic(III) is oxidised to arsenic(V), antimony(III) to antimony(V), tin(II) to tin(IV), mercury(I) to mercury(II), ferrocyanide to ferricyanide, sulphite to sulphate, ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid, hydroquinone to quinone, and phenol and aniline are tribrominated in presence of potassium bromide. The following equations show the modes of oxidation of other reductants, viz., thiocyanate and its three complexes, hydrazine and its two derivatives, semicarbazide, thiosemicarbazide and thiourea.

DIH has got definite advantages over earlier developed dichloramine-T, dibromamine-T and chlorbromamine-T. Thiocyanate and the three complex thiocyanates studied here could be determined by direct potentiometric titrations using DIH, whereas these could be determined by excess back titrations using dichloramine-T, dibromamine-T, and chlorbromamine-T. This added reactivity of DIH helps to determine more reductants by direct titration methods.

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Extractive Microdetermination of Chromium(VI) with N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic Acid

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SEVERAL reagents have been employed for the solvent extraction studies of chromium(VI)¹⁻⁸. However, these methods suffer from many disadvantages. They need critical control of acidity, large volume of the organic phase, longer time for equilibration and are deficient at microgram level of chromium. Tributyl phosphate⁹ was also used for the extraction of Cr(VI) but the complex was found to be unstable. Extraction of Cr(VI) with long chain amines was also reported¹⁰, but had very low molar absorptivity ($\epsilon = 20 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Gallacetophone oxime¹¹ is a new spectrophotometric reagent used for the determination of Cr(VI). The molar absorptivity of this method ($\epsilon = 3.6 \times 10^3$) is about ten times smaller than that of the present method ($\epsilon = 3.4 \times 10^4$). Recently Cr(VI) has been extracted with tetraphenylarsonium chloride¹². But this method suffers from the disadvantage that anions like MnO_4^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ interfere in the determination.

In the present communication a new reagent N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) is used for extraction of Cr(VI). A yellow coloured